

Synthesis of Furano Compounds. Part XXXVII. On the Condensation of 2:3-Dichloro Naphthoquinone with 1:4-Isochromandione

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It is shown that the condensation of 2:3-dichloronaphthoquinone with 1,4-isochromandione in pyridine leads to the pyrrocoline (II). An unequivocal synthesis of (III) has also been achieved. The supposed intermediate (XII) in the formation of the furo-*isocoumarin* (XVI) from ψ -trimethylbrazilone has been synthesised.

Only a very limited number of furo-*isocoumarins* has been described in literature¹⁻⁶ and they have not been studied in any considerable detail. The present communication deals with the study on the synthesis of furo(3',2' : 3,4)-*isocoumarins* and this has led to the revision of the structure of the so called 7,12-dihydro-5,7,12-trioxo-5H-naphtho-(2',3' : 4,5) furo(3,2-c)*isochromen* (I) described by Buu-Hoi *et al.*⁶. These workers have reported the formation of the furo-*isocoumarin* (I), m.p. 230° resulting from the condensation of 2,3-dichloronaphthoquinone and isochroman-1,4-dione in the presence of pyridine under reflux.

On repetition of their experiment, we obtained a compound, m.p. 268° which had the expected, C, H, analytical value as reported by Buu-Hoi *et al.* but, surprisingly, the compound contained nitrogen. It was obvious that the pyridine played a role in the reaction to give a fundamentally different structure and a reinvestigation was in order.

The reactions of this compound, as well as the results of elementary analysis are consistent with the proposal that the compound was really 1-(*o*-carboxybenzoyl)-2,3-phthaloyl-pyrrocoline (II). Thus the compound was converted into its methyl ester (III) with

1. D. N. Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **35**, 621.
2. J. H. Birkinshaw, P. Chaplen, A. H. Manchanda and R. Raino-Martin, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1965, 29.
3. J. Grimshaw, R. D. Haworth and H. K. Pindred, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 833.
4. R. D. Haworth and J. M. McLachlan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 1503.
5. W. H. Perkin and R. Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, **95**, 389.
6. N. P. Buu-Hoi, J. P. Hoeffinger and P. Jacquignon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, Part V, 6105.

diazomethane and was degraded to α -picolinic acid which was confirmed by the colour test with cyanogen bromide and β -naphthylamine. The compound did not afford any crystalline product on reductive acetylation.

The mass spectrum of the ester (III) is in agreement with the proposed structure. The main peaks can be assigned as follows: m/e 409 = M^+ , 378 = $M-OCH_3$, 350 = $M-COCH_3$, 274 = IV, 204.5 = M^{++} , 189 = $(M-OCH_3)^{++}$, 163 = V, 161 = $(350-CO)^{++}$. The peak at m/e 190 is somewhat difficult to explain, perhaps loss of 3CO from the ion, m/e 274 (2CO from the quinone moiety) leads to the corresponding ion. The two acylium ions m/e

274 and 163, respectively confirm the presence of the acyclic ketone group. The infrared spectrum showed absorption at 1724, 1676 and 1664 cm^{-1} for the ester, quinone and aromatic ketone carbonyl respectively. Its N.M.R. spectrum showed proton signal at τ 6.4 (singlet, 3H, $COOCH_3$) for the methyl ester. Two aromatic protons appeared around τ 0.01 and 1.5. These low values are due to the deshielding effect of the quinone carbonyl groups on these protons (H_x and H_y).

The final confirmation of the structure was achieved by an unequivocal synthesis of the ester (III) by the condensation of 2,3-dichloronaphthoquinone and *o*-methoxycarbonylacetophenone in presence of pyridine under reflux⁷. The superimposable infra-red spectrum of (III) with that of this authentic ester and the undepressed mixed melting point of the two leave little doubt about its structure.

7. R. V. Acharya, B. Suryanarayana and B. D. Tilak, *J. Sci. Industr. Res.*, 1955, **14B**, 396.

It is suggested that the formation of (II) proceeds *via* displacement of one of the chlorine atoms of the dichloronaphthoquinone by hydrogen of the active methylene group at 3-position of *isochroman-1,4-dione* and displacement of the other by pyridine to give the key intermediate (VI). A nucleophilic attack at the activated position of the pyridine ring by the carbanion formed by loss of a proton from the highly activated methyne group of (VI) would give (II) as mechanistically shown.

Whatever may be the mechanism, the formation of (II) is doubtlessly facilitated by the resonance stabilisation arising from contribution of structure (VII) and (VIII).

Another furo(3',2' : 3,4)-*isocoumarin* compound has been reported by Perkin and Robinson⁵ who treated ψ -trimethylbrazilone (IX) with potassium hypobromite to give the trimethoxycoumarono-*isocoumarin* hydrobromide (XI), which readily lost hydrogen bromide on boiling in chloroform or acetic acid affording (XII). The mechanism suggested by Bentley⁸ involves intermediate (X, R = H).

8. K. W. Bentley, *The Natural Pigments*, Interscience Publishers, Inc., 1960, page 85.

If (X, R = H) is an intermediate in this conversion, the same compound (XI) is expected to be formed, if (X, R = H) is treated with potassium hypobromite. The methyl ester (X, R = CH₃) was synthesised by the condensation of (XIII) and (XIV) in presence of Et₃N at room temperature.

The infra-red spectrum of (X, R = CH₃) showed absorption at 1780 cm⁻¹ (lactone carbonyl) and 1715 cm⁻¹ (ester carbonyl) and the N.M.R. spectrum showed three singlets at 7.5-9.5, 6.08 and 6.5 in the integral ratio of 1 : 2 : 1 due to the methoxyl group at 6-position, two methoxyl groups at 4' and 5'-positions (6H, merging into a singlet), and methyl ester (3H, COOCH₃) respectively. Its mass spectrum showed an intense molecular ion peak at m/e 370. Other ions corresponded to peaks at m/e 355, 339, 327, and 311. But unfortunately (X, R = CH₃) on treatment with potassium hypobromite did not yield (XI), instead a dibromo compound, which may be attributed the structure (XV), on the basis of elemental analysis and i.r. data.

So these experiments reveal the fact that the conversion does not proceed *via* the above intermediate steps but it follows a somewhat different mechanism.

EXPERIMENTAL

1-(*o*-Carboxybenzoyl)-2,3-phthaloylpyrrocoline(II): A solution of isochroman-1,4-dione⁹ (1.0 g.) and the dichloronaphthoquinone (1.0 g.) in pyridine (10.0 ml) was refluxed for 24 hrs, the solvent distilled off in vacuo, the residue diluted with water, filtered and crystallised from ethanol giving reddish prisms (0.9 g.), m.p. 268° (Found : C, 72.56; H, 3.50; N, 3.83 : C₂₄H₁₃O₅N requires C, 72.91; H, 3.29; N, 5.85%). Major i.r. peaks are at 1705 cm⁻¹ (acid carbonyl), 1688 cm⁻¹ (quinone carbonyl) and 1672 cm⁻¹ (aromatic ketone carbonyl).

1-(*o*-Methoxycarbonylbenzoyl)2,3-phthaloylpyrrocoline(III): The acid (II) was treated with ethereal solution of diazomethane (10.0 ml) prepared from nitrosomethylurea (1.0 g.) and left overnight. The excess diazomethane was decomposed with a few drops of glacial acetic acid, washed with saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate, dried over anhydrous MgSO₄ and solvent evaporated to give the *methyl ester* (III) (0.3 g.). On repeated

9. E. B. Knott, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 402.

crystallisation from acetic acid it afforded reddish needles, m.p. 194–95° having identical i.r. spectrum with synthetic ester. (Found : C, 73.2; H, 3.8; N, 3.5 : C₂₅H₁₅O₅N requires C, 73.3; H, 3.7; N, 3.4%).

Oxidative degradation: The acid (II; 0.1 g.) was refluxed with aqueous potassium permanganate (0.4 g. in 20.0 ml) and 10% sodium hydroxide solution (4.0 ml) for 6 hrs and then cooled. Excess of potassium permanganate was destroyed by addition of a few drops of alcohol, the precipitated manganese dioxide filtered off, and the colourless filtrate was made strongly alkaline and concentrated. The concentrated solution was acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid till just acidic, evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure and the residue extracted with absolute alcohol (6.0 ml). A mixture of this solution (1.0 ml), a crystal of cyanogen bromide and a little β -naphthylamine was warmed slightly whereby orange colour developed. This indicated the presence of α -picolinic acid⁷.

1-(o-Methoxycarbonylbenzoyl)-2 : 3-phthaloylpyrrocoline(III): A mixture of 2 : 3-dichloronaphthoquinone (2.27 g.) and dry pyridine (8.0 ml) was heated on a boiling water bath for 30 mins. *o*-Methoxycarbonylacetophenone (1.8 g.) was added and the mixture heated for 15 mins on boiling water bath and then refluxed for 1 hr. After cooling, the solution was diluted with water and extracted with ether, dried (MgSO₄) and solvent evaporated to yield a dark red product (1.1 g.) which on repeated crystallisation from acetic acid yielded reddish needles, m.p. 195°, undepressed mixed m.p. with the previous ester from the acid (II) and giving a superimposable i.r. spectrum.

2'-Methoxycarbonyl-4',5'-dimethoxybenzylidene-6-methoxybenzofuran-2-one(X, R = CH₃): 6-Methoxybenzofuran-2-one¹⁰ (0.2 g.) and methyl *m*-opiate¹¹ (0.27 g.) was dissolved in absolute ethanol (3.0 ml) and a drop of triethylamine added, shaken and left overnight at room temperature. Next day, the solution was concentrated and cooled to yield product (0.13 g.) which on crystallisation from benzene afforded fine lemon yellow needles, m.p. 195° (Found : C, 64.49; H, 5.56; C₂₀H₁₃O₇ requires : C, 64.86; H, 4.86%). Infra-red spectrum showed bands at 1780 cm⁻¹ (lactone carbonyl), and 1715 cm⁻¹ (ester carbonyl).

Potassium hypobromite oxidation of (X, R = CH₃): A well-cooled solution of (X, R = CH₃; 0.2 g.) in 30% potassium hydroxide solution was poured into potassium hypobromite solution prepared by dissolving bromine (1.0 ml) in 12% potassium hydroxide solution (2.1 ml) and powdered ice (ca. 2.0 g.) and allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. Next day, saturated solution of sodium bisulphite (5.0 ml) was added and acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The solid (0.15 g.) separated was filtered, and crystallised from acetic acid to yield pale yellow crystals, m.p. 250° (Found : C, 43.84; H, 3.07 : C₁₉H₁₆O₇Br₂ requires C, 44.18; H, 3.10%). Infra-red spectrum showed absorption at 1785 cm⁻¹ (lactone carbonyl).

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10. J. N. Chatterjea, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **34**, 304.
11. J. J. Brown and G. T. Newbold, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 400.

